

D7.6 – Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholders Engagement Final Report

Version 1.0

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Translation
BIOEXCEL	CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE FOR BIOMOLECULAR RESEARCH
CALMIP	CALCUL EN MIDI-PYRÉNÉES
CECAM	CENTRE EUROPÉEN DE CALCUL ATOMIQUE ET MOLÉCULAIRE
CINECA	CINECA CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO
COE	CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE
CoE	CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE
CSA	COORDINATION SUPPORT ACTION
ENCCS	EUROCC NATIONAL COMPETENCE CENTER SWEDEN
EU	EUROPEAN UNION
EUROHPC JU	EUROPEAN HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPUTING JOINT UNDERTAKING
F2F	FACE-TO-FACE
HPC	HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPUTING
HPC3	HPC CENTER OF EXCELLENCE COUNCIL
HPDA	HIGH PERFORMANCE DATA ANALYTICS
IPSAS	INSTITUTE OF PHYSICS, SLOVAK ACADEMY OF SCIENCES
KPI	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATOR
LUMI	LARGE UNIFIED MODERN INFRASTRUCTURE
ML	MACHINE LEARNING
NCC	EUROPEAN NATIONAL COMPETENCE CENTERS
NOMAD	THE NOVEL MATERIALS DISCOVERY
PRACE	PARTNERSHIP FOR ADVANCED COMPUTING IN EUROPE
Psi-k	AB INITIO (FROM ELECTRONIC STRUCTURE) CALCULATION OF COMPLEX PROCESS IN MATERIALS
QMC	QUANTUM MONTE CARLO
SISSA	INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL FOR ADVANCED STUDIES
TREX	TARGETING REAL CHEMICAL ACCURACY AT THE EXASCALE
TCCM	THEORETICAL CHEMISTRY AND COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING
UT	UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE
UVSQ	UNIVERSITÉ DE VERSAILLES-SAINT-QUENTIN-EN YVELINES
WP	WORK PACKAGE

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Executive Summary

Since its start in 2020 the TREX Center of Excellence (CoE) has increased the awareness of the accurate QMC stochastic sampling methods in the European electronic structure community. Via training and education, a new generation of young people with expertise in QMC methods and large-scale computing was created, trained and made knowledgeable in scientific research QMC applications as well as in the HPC development methodologies. TREX generated an integrated HPC software platform of codes and libraries which are expected to last for years, and they are bound to strongly affect the development of the QMC community and electronic structure community as a whole in the future. Last but not least, as a result of the expertise provided by the TREX partners, a range of very valuable scientific results and papers was generated.

By adopting a co-design approach and by feeding young scientists with a “quantum Monte Carlo culture”, TREX has been a multifaceted project whose findings could be highly beneficial for the chemistry and condensed matter research communities as well as the HPC industry and commercial providers.

This document demonstrates the impact generated by the project by engaging with different stakeholders, establishing meaningful connections and foster engagement. This document serves as the final version of the communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement plan for the TREX project, falling under WP7, covering the period from M19 (April 2022) to M42 (March 2024). It builds upon the “*D7.4 Communication, Dissemination, and Stakeholder Engagement Interim Report and User Uptake Update*” submitted in M19, providing a final update on TREX’s communication, dissemination and engagement activities performed up to M42.

The document is structured in four main sections:

- Section 1 summarises the main communication and dissemination achievements and the activities implemented to promote and disseminate TREX results & assets
- Section 2 describes the results of the stakeholder engagement performed via TREX workshops and events
- Section 3 reports on participation of TREX partners in HPC events
- Section 4 provides further details and outcomes of communication activities.

Additionally, Annex I lists the events organised by TREX and third-party events attended by the TREX team, while Annex II presents the scientific papers published by the TREX team, and Annex III lists the participants to the TREX Symposium.

1. Main Achievements from M1-M42

WP7 was responsible for the overall dissemination and engagement activities of the TREX CoE. According to the overall goal of the “TREX Communication, dissemination, and stakeholders engagement strategy and plan” (D7.3), the actions put in place during the 42 months of the project aimed at disseminating TREX exploitable results to the targeted stakeholders throughout different channels. The WP7 activities undertaken until M42 were part of a collaborative effort of all TREX partners, and closely connected with the training and educational activities of WP6.

Through active engagement with key stakeholders, the document illustrates the tangible impact generated by the project in terms of stakeholders engaged and trained via schools and conferences, scientific publications disseminated, online engagement through events and webinars, branding identity and informative materials produced. Figure 1 concisely outlines the primary achievements of TREX to date (M1-M42).

In this reporting period, the following outcomes have been achieved:

- Consolidation of TREX **project branding** and visual identity within the European HPC community
- The maintenance and continuous update of a **fully-fledged website** as the core of its communication strategy to showcase the main results of the project and announce its community activities.
- A wide **social media community of over 1000+ individuals and networks** following TREX accounts and which played a key role in sharing news and achievements with other projects, users, and the broad HPC community.

The main outcome of the dissemination and outreach activities is the engagement of a **broad community of Quantum Monte Carlo experts**. This community encompasses Postdocs and PhD students directly trained in the groups participating in TREX CoE, as well as participants of the various schools and workshops organised by TREX. Ultimately a broad group of **500 individuals engaged**, including PhD students, postdoc, permanent fellows, master students, researchers and engineers, students and scientific staff in general within the European context. This community was fed **with a “quantum Monte Carlo culture”**, making them aware of the appealing features of a stochastic way of approaching the many-body problem in quantum physics and chemistry, achieved mainly through direct interaction at workshops and schools.

Figure 1 TREX in Numbers (M1-M42)

1.1. Promotion and dissemination of TREX results & assets

The promotion of TREX results is at the core of the project dissemination plan and its activities. In this Section, we detail how the activities listed below have been promoted and disseminated.

TREX libraries for software developers and HPC experts

TREX places a strong emphasis on open-access resources and collaborative development, with the two libraries, QMCKI and TREXIO, providing essential tools for researchers in the field. This section delves into the outreach efforts and recognition garnered by these libraries, demonstrating their impact on both the scientific community and the broader landscape of high-performance computing.

To ensure sustainability and open access, dedicated webpages for TREX libraries have been created both on GitHub and on the TREX website. These serve as central hubs, offering open access to the libraries and providing extensive documentation for users and developers alike.

Figure 2 TREX Libraries pages on website and GitHub

During TREX's lifetime the two libraries were highly disseminated through a series of third-party events across Europe and beyond with presentations, posters and practical demos. Among the most relevant events where the library was disseminated are:

- **EuroHPC Summit Week, March 2022**¹ where QMCKI was presented as an ideal tool for chemical researchers not only in regards to performance but also energy consumption while maintaining numerical accuracy.
- **CECAM workshop, October 2022**² where both QMCKI and TREXIO were presented in a dedicated session of the workshop entitled "Library development and co-design" and also disseminated through a poster session³.
- **10th edition OpenMolcas developers' workshop**⁴, June 2022, where TREXIO was presented as a possible way of collaboration format with the OpenMolcas environment⁵.
- **WATOC**⁶, July 2022, where TREXIO was presented in a poster session⁷.

Furthermore, a scientific article about TREXIO was published on the esteemed Journal of Chemical Physics Volume 158, Issue 17⁸, acknowledging the academic standing of TREX research but also underscoring its critical role in enabling collaboration and ensuring reproducibility in quantum chemistry research.

1.2. TREX Flagship Codes

In addition to the QMCKI and TREXIO libraries, the work of the TREX Centre of Excellence targeted six different codes belonging to the scientific domain of quantum chemistry electronic structure: **NECI, GammCor, TurboRVB, CHAMP, QMC=Chem, Quantum Package**. The promotion of all these codes continued during the second reporting period along with their evolution.

Figure 3 TREX Flagship Code logos

The website section dedicated to the codes was revamped, with dedicated pages where to find technical information on each code, technical specification and documentation, training materials available as well as downloadable versions of each code. Codes were also part of a continuous social media campaign, with target posts dedicated to each of the codes.

¹ <https://trex-coe.eu/events/eurohpc-summit-week-2022>

² <https://trex-coe.eu/events/co-design-hpc-computational-materials-and-molecular-science>

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/7180354>

⁴ <https://trex-coe.eu/events/10th-edition-openmolcas-developers-workshop>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6624127>

⁶ <https://trex-coe.eu/events/watoc-2020>

⁷ <https://www.xcdsystem.com/cic/program/s07pZsO/index.cfm?pgid=1913&sid=25176&abid=89250>

⁸ <https://pubs.aip.org/aip/jcp/article-abstract/158/17/174801/2888846/TREXIO-A-file-format-and-library-for-quantum?redirectedFrom=fulltext>

Figure 4 TREX Flagship Codes - Social Promotion

In line with the aim of promoting awareness, engagement, and adoption of its flagship codes among the scientific community, TREX has been active in showcasing the capabilities and applications of these codes, facilitating knowledge exchange and driving advancements in computational research through strategic activities including joint cooperation with relevant initiatives, participation and organisations of different types of events, scientific publications and more. Some highlights of these activities carried out in the reporting period are reported below.

Quantum Package:

- In **June 2022** TREX promoted Quantum Package through initiatives like the "**QMC Hands-on Summer Workshop**"⁹, conducted in collaboration with the National Competence Centre for HPC (NCC for HPC). These workshops offered a blend of lectures and tutorials, empowering attendees to explore Quantum Package's functionalities firsthand.
- In partnership with the EuroHPC National Competence Centre Sweden (ENCCS), on the 1st of **March 2023** TREX organised a workshop titled "**Targeting chemical accuracy with quantum Monte Carlo on LUMI**"¹⁰. This event provided participants with hands-on experience using Quantum Package on the LUMI supercomputer, amplifying their understanding of quantum chemistry's practical applications.

CHAMP:

- CHAMP made its mark at the **PSI-K Conference, from 22 to 25 August 2022** in the SwissTech Convention Center at EPFL in Lausanne (Switzerland), emphasising its role in championing stochastic electronic structure methods.
- CHAMP was among the main TREX codes offered to participants at the "**TREX Workshop on Code Tuning for the Exascale**"¹¹, co-organized by TREX and several European National Competence Centres for HPC from **5 to 7 June 2023** at the Slovak Academy of Sciences campus, in Bratislava, Slovakia. Using CHAMP as an optimization target, the MAQAO framework was showcased as an essential tool for code optimization, providing participants with invaluable insights into code tuning.
- Still in **June 2023** CHAMP was highly showcased at the **MESA+ Meeting** at the Kinopolis cinema in Enschede, The Netherlands. the Computational Chemical Physics (CCP) group at University of Twente presented the TREX poster titled "**Drunk and honest: random electrons for accurate excited states and molecular dynamics**"¹².

⁹ <https://trex-coe.eu/events/qmc-hands-summer-workshop-0>

¹⁰ <https://trex-coe.eu/news/successful-workshop-quantum-monte-carlo-lumi-and-trex-coe-paving-way-future-collaborative>

¹¹ <https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-workshop-code-tuning-exascale>

¹² <https://trex-coe.eu/index.php/news/drunk-and-honest-trex-champ-qmc-package-presented-computational-chemical-physics-ccp-group>

QMC=CHEM:

- QMC=CHEM was prominently featured at the "**Workshop on Software Co-Design Actions in European Flagship HPC Codes**". This event facilitated knowledge sharing among European HPC Centre Of Excellence, using QMC=CHEM's to showcase performance analysis across different architectures.

NECI:

- NECI played a pivotal role in the OpenMolcas community, contributing to the advancement of computational chemistry through collaborative efforts and knowledge sharing. The result of the interaction is reported in the publication "**The OpenMolcas Web: A Community-Driven Approach to Advancing Computational Chemistry**"¹³ published in the Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation in April 2023.

GAMMCOR:

- GAMMCOR was one of the main TREX codes presented at the "**TREX Workshop on Electronic Structure Methods for Strong Correlation**"¹⁴ from **18 to 20 April 2023**. This event provided a platform for researchers to explore the theoretical foundations and computational algorithms behind GAMMCOR, fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration within the scientific community.
- Additionally, GAMMCOR was a focal point of discussion at the "**TREX Hackathon III**"¹⁵ from 6 to 8 March 2023, where participants deep dive into GPU optimization techniques and explored opportunities for code enhancement with specific support of both Intel and Nvidia representatives.

TurboRVB:

- A groundbreaking scientific article titled "**Quantum Phase Diagram of High-Pressure Hydrogen**"¹⁶ showcased the transformative potential of TurboRVB in computational physics and was published in the prestigious Nature Physics journal in **March 2023**. Through meticulous calculations and advanced computational methods, the research team unveiled critical insights into the behaviour of high-pressure hydrogen, offering valuable guidance for experimental investigations. TurboRVB's capacity in performing large-scale calculations was instrumental in achieving unparalleled accuracy and predictability.
- Furthermore, TurboRVB took centre stage at the "**TREX School on QMC with TurboRVB**"¹⁷ from **3 to 7 July 2023**, where it was unveiled as an open-source package after years of development. This milestone marked a significant step forward in TurboRVB's journey, making it more accessible to researchers and scientists worldwide.

¹³ <https://chemrxiv.org/engage/chemrxiv/article-details/643698c473c6563f14b690f2>

¹⁴ <https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-workshop-electronic-structure-methods-strong-correlation-theory-computational>

¹⁵ <https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-hackathon-iii>

¹⁶ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41567-023-01960-5>

¹⁷ <https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-school-qmc-turborvb-2023>

2. TREX community building: Stakeholder engagement via workshops and events

One of the key pillars of TREX was an outreach programme to reach out to the relevant developers' and users' communities to foster the use of the developed HPC codes as well as engage and forge a new generation of highly skilled computational scientists. Thanks to a continuous training activity, TREX acknowledged a steady increase in the numbers of QMC method practitioners. Over 500 participants took part in the [Webinars, Schools, Workshops and Hackathons](#) organised by TREX.

The TREX team has organised and co-organised a total of 15 events (Webinars, Schools, Workshops, Hackathons), eight of which were held from M19 (April 2022) until M41 (February 2024). For each of the events the following activities were implemented as part of the engagement campaign in collaboration with WP6:

- **Promotional materials:** for each event, branded event banners and digital visuals were designed to be reused in the online engagement campaigns. TREX branded t-shirts were designed and distributed to in-presence training schools. Flyers were distributed, too.
- **Agenda:** WP7 collaborated closely with the partners in charge of the organisation of each event to define the timing and goals, setting audience expectations and categories of discussion.
- **Registration and logistics:** WP7 set-up registration processes on the TREX website, including poster application procedures when poster sessions were planned. For the online events, rehearsals before the event were organised to ensure smooth presentations and address any technical issues.
- **Engagement campaigns:** Social media, newsletter and direct email campaigns were implemented to promote the events reaching communities through channels and related HPC communities such as psi-K, CECAM, EuroCC communities (see chapter 4). WP7 communicated with registered participants via email and live-tweeted during the event.
- **Post-event activities:** Post-event reports summarising outputs and recommendations were written and published online, including outcomes of participants surveys when agreed with the event organisers. Follow-up messages to participants and speakers were shared within 48 hours, also pointing to recorded videos when available.
- **Video recordings:** When agreed, recordings of online events were published on the event page and TREX YouTube channel as soon as the recording was available.

Overall TREX physical and online events garnered significant interest from around the globe, attracting over 500 participants representing 67 countries, coming from 26 EU and 39 Non-EU regions.

Figure 5 Participants at TREX Events

In the following section more details are provided for all the events organised.

2.1. TREX Workshops and Schools

WP7 supported TREX training activities under WP6 “Training and User Uptake” lead by IPSAS, aiming to increase the expertise of the wider community not only in the scientific application and HPC usage of TREX software but also more generally in HPC, democratising the use of upcoming computational (pre)exascale resources.

2.1.1. QMC Hands-On Summer Workshop. June 2022

This workshop served as the first physical event organised by the TREX team following the COVID-19 pandemic. In partnership with the Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAS), Institute of Physics SAS (IPSAS), and National Competence Centre for High Performance Computing (NCC for HPC), it was conducted in a hybrid format from 20 to 23 June 2022, in Mojmírovce, Slovakia. The workshop brought together 21 PhD and Master's students from Europe and beyond, providing them with a unique opportunity to gain insight into the world of QMC (Quantum Monte Carlo) and to interact with some of the foremost experts in the field.

WP7 assisted WP6 in organising this event by undertaking various pre-event activities, including setting up the event page, agenda structure, registration platform, poster contest procedures and submission platform, and preparing prizes for the poster winner.

Throughout the event, we offered onsite technical and communication support, which encompassed social media promotions, organisation of the poster sessions, and recording the workshop proceedings.

Figure 6 QMC workshop in Mojmírovce - Highlights

Following the event, WP7 continued its involvement by ensuring the publication of the workshop recording, satisfaction survey, and a post-event news article¹⁸ highlighting the workshop's key

¹⁸ <https://www.trex-coe.eu/news/trex-qmc-workshop-post-event-report>

moments. Additionally, WP7 oversaw the publication of submitted posters and collected testimonials from attendees for dissemination.

Victor Vysotskiy, a Doctoral student at eSENCE: The e-Science Collaboration at Lund University in Sweden, won the QMC Hands-on Summer Workshop's Poster contest.

Figure 7 QMC Workshop Poster Winner

2.1.2. TREX workshop on electronic structure methods for strong correlation: theory, computational algorithms, and codes. April 2023

The TREX Workshop on Quantum-Chemical Methods for Strongly Correlated Systems was held at the Institute of Physics, Lodz University of Technology in Poland from 18 to 20 April, 2023. WP7 employed various communication activities to promote engagement and participation, starting with the establishment of an online registration system, streamlining the enrollment process for interested applicants. Subsequently, acceptance letters were created and dispatched to the selected 30 participants, ensuring transparency and acknowledgment of their participation.

Figure 8 TREX participants to Lodz workshop

A visually appealing and informative flyer¹⁹ was designed and circulated to attract registrations at a local level, while on a digital level, WP7 took care of social media promotion campaigns as well as dedicated newsletters providing detailed information about the workshop's objectives, agenda, and the expertise of speakers and tutors. Beyond this, strategic publications on external channels, including Psi-k²⁰, were leveraged to tap into broader networks and communities interested in quantum chemistry and correlated systems.

Following the workshop, a satisfaction survey sent to the participants revealed that they particularly appreciated the combination of lectures and tutorials and the personalised guidance received during the event. Key takeaways and feedback from the participants have been summarised in a post-event report²¹ published on the TREX website.

2.1.3. Code Tuning for the Exascale, June 2023

TREX hosted the "Code Tuning for the Exascale" workshop from 5-7 June 2023 in Bratislava, Slovakia, in collaboration with the Austrian, Czech, and Slovak National Competence Centres for HPC. This workshop gathered 22 code developers who had the opportunity to learn about various techniques, methods, and solutions to enhance performance and scalability across diverse platforms.

¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/7784062>

²⁰ <https://psi-k.net/trex-workshop-on-electronic-structure-methods-for-strong-correlation-theory-computational-algorithms-and-codes/>

²¹ <https://trex-coe.eu/news/exploring-quantum-chemical-methods-strongly-correlated-systems-insights-trex-workshop>

Figure 9 TREX participants to Code Tuning Workshop in Bratislava

WP7 supported WP6 in organising this event in terms of communication and dissemination of pre- and post-event activities, specifically the publication of the event page²², presentations, and a news article²³ providing insights and experiences from the event.

2.1.4. TREX School on QMC with TurboRVB. July 2023

The event was run from July 3 to July 7, 2023 at the Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati (SISSA) in Trieste, Italy.

WP7 assisted the event organisers in setting up the event's webpage, the registration process and to communicate with the selected participants providing them with the necessary information for a seamless experience. Furthermore, WP7 took care of the outreach activities with dedicated social media, newsletters and dissemination of the event announcement in external sources such as Psi-k²⁴ and Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe (PRACE)²⁵.

The event received 65 valid applications from Master and PhD students, postdocs, researchers, and HPC experts, of which 27 were then selected to participate in the event spanning lectures and hands-on sessions.

²² <https://trex-coe.eu/events/trex-workshop-code-tuning-exascale>

²³ <https://trex-coe.eu/news/insights-and-experiences-recap-trex-workshop-code-tuning-exascale>

²⁴ <https://psi-k.net/trex-school-on-qmc-with-turborvb/>

²⁵ <https://hpc-portal.eu/node/1720>

Figure 10 Participants to TREX School on QMC with TurboRVB in Trieste

The poster presentation session was undoubtedly a highlight of the event, featuring over 20 participants from diverse backgrounds across Europe and beyond, highlighting the future possibilities that quantum materials research holds.

The Best Poster prize, a one-week stay at Sorbonne University, Paris, in the Quantum Theory of Materials group (IMPMC), was won by Liam Bernheimer from Tel Aviv University. His poster, **“Path Integration, Lexicographic Symmetrization, and Derivative-Free Energy Estimation Within the Stochastic Representation of Wavefunctions”**²⁶, addressed stability and symmetry challenges, offering insights into particle statistics, density, and interactions in fermions and bosons.

The second place was earned by Abdul Ghaffar from the Japan Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (JAIST) with the poster, **“Advancements in Ternary Hydrides: Predictive Modeling of Y-Th-H System for High-Tc Superconductivity”**²⁷, highlighted the potential of ternary hydrides in advancing high-Tc superconductivity, particularly in complex systems.

Finally, the third prize was assigned to Davide Piccioni from SISSA with the poster **“A Jastrow wave function for the spin-1 Heisenberg chain: string order revealed by the mapping to the classical Coulomb gas”**²⁸ introducing a method to describe the properties and topological features of the Spin-1 Heisenberg chain.

²⁶ https://trex-coe.eu/sites/default/files/2023-06/Liam_Bernheimer_abstract.pdf

²⁷ https://trex-coe.eu/sites/default/files/2023-06/Abdul_Ghaffar_poster.pdf

²⁸ https://trex-coe.eu/sites/default/files/2023-06/Davide_Piccioni_abstract.pdf

Inspiring Excellence: Celebrating the Achievements of TREX School QMC TurboRVB 2023 Poster Winners

At TREX School QMC TurboRVB 2023, a showcase of innovation, dedication, and expertise unfolded as participants engaged in a dynamic exploration of quantum materials and computation. The event not only served as a platform for learning but also celebrated the talents of those who exhibited their groundbreaking research through the poster competition.

Figure 11 TREX School on QMC with TurboRVB in Trieste - Poster Winners

2.2. TREX Hackathons

After the first two successful hackathons organised in the first reporting period (November 2021, March 2022), two additional TREX Hackathons were organised in this reporting period as hands-on workshops to train code developers. They are detailed in the following paragraphs.

2.2.1. TREX Hackathon III. March 2023

The third TREX Hackathon was held in Bologna from 06-08 March 2023 hosted by TREX partner CINECA. The event brought together 11 TREX code developers for three days, focusing on porting their codes to operate on GPUs or optimising existing GPU-compatible applications. The event, tailored for the TREX consortium, included theoretical sessions on GPU architectures, practical exercises on Marconi100, and invaluable insights from experts external to the TREX Consortium, i.e. Matt Bettencourt (NVIDIA) and Giacomo Rossi (Intel). Hands-on achievements included running `qmckl_gpu` on Marconi's V100 and advancing TurboRVB and CHAMP integration.

Figure 12 TREX participants at the TREX Hackathon III

In support to WP6, WP7 created the official event page on the TREX website, as an entry point to all the presentations and training materials²⁹, and followed up with social media promotion.

2.2.2. TREX Hackathon IV. October 2023

The TREX Hackathon IV was organised in a physical format from 16 to 20 October 2023 at the premises of TREX partner Megware in Oberdeck, Chemnitz (Germany). The consortium took the opportunity of this event to organise a first face-to-face (F2F) meeting including all TREX participants, which followed the Hackathon on the 3rd and 4th days of the event (19-20 October). WP7 attended the event and ensured live social media posting.

²⁹ <https://www.trex-coe.eu/events/trex-hackathon-iii>

Figure 13 TREX Hackathon IV - Highlights

2.3. TREX Webinars

In this reporting period TREX has organised three webinars, spotlighting the advancements in its flagship QMC codes and open-source libraries optimised for upcoming Exascale systems to an audience of 240+ participants, new to the TREX community, from 52 different countries.

Figure 14 TREX Webinars previews

Figure 15 Geographical overview of participants registered to the 3 TREX Webinars

Top 10 countries	Number of registered users
India	35
Italy	22
United States	20
France	18
United Kingdom	14
Switzerland	12
Russia	10
Germany	10
Croatia	10
Morocco	7

Figure 16 Top 10 countries of provenance of participants registered to the 3 TREX Webinars

The first webinar “**TREX High Performance Software Solutions for Quantum Mechanical Simulations at the Exascale**” was held on 8 February 2023. The agenda guided participants through the TREX six different quantum chemistry codes, and the open-source libraries optimised for upcoming Exascale systems. The webinar demonstrated how the TREX codes and libraries could positively impact the Exascale transition, and gave firsthand insights from code users' experiences. 40 participants attended the event.

The second webinar "**Quantum Monte Carlo HPC Applications in Condensed Matter, Quantum Chemistry, and Materials Science,**" was held on January 25, 2024, was co-organised with the Centre Européen de Calcul Atomique et Moléculaire (CECAM). The webinar explored the frontiers of quantum materials research and quantum chemistry, by means of Quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) calculations, owing to their unique suitability in solving complex many-body problems as well as in harnessing the parallelism offered by upcoming exascale supercomputer architectures. The agenda covered a spectrum of key topics, including magnetism, surface physics, layered materials, energy excitations, and high-pressure hydrogen. The collaboration with CECAM turned out to be very effective both in terms of quality and variety of the content delivered as well as in terms of engagement achieved, with 145 participants registered.

The third webinar titled “**TREX High Performance Software Solutions for Quantum Mechanical Simulations at the Exascale**” was organised later on the 20th of February 2024, in order to provide users with the most updated information about the very recent developments of the TREX codes. 57 participants registered for this latest webinar.

Figure 17 shows some of the live Twitter coverages during the webinars.

Figure 17 TREX Webinars - Social Promotion

2.4. Bridging Quantum Monte Carlo and High-Performance Simulations: Symposium 2024

Between 5 and 9 February 2024 TREX brought together in Luxembourg Quantum Monte Carlo experts from across Europe and overseas to celebrate the project's achievements, discuss ongoing challenges and foresee the future of simulations in chemistry and materials science. Under the coordination of Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology, which was also the local host of the event, and with collaboration and inputs from all TREX partners, the final event brought together a diverse group of participants, from seasoned researchers to promising PhD students, representing the forefront of Quantum Monte Carlo technology. All participants engaged and contributed to the rich pool of keynotes and sessions.

Figure 18 TREX Coordinator Claudia Filippi welcoming the audience of the TREX Symposium, Luxembourg, 5 February 2024

The Symposium highlighted the potential, along with challenges, for scaling Quantum Monte Carlo methods to the power of exascale computing. The event was opened by Claudia Filippi, University of Twente and TREX Coordinator, followed by Mladen Skelin (EuroHPC JU), who gave an overview of the EuroHPC JU, the recent agreements with HPC centres in Europe, financial support provided so far and upcoming funding opportunities. Dr David Ceperley, University of Illinois Urbana Champaign (US) and one of the most experienced researchers in Quantum Monte Carlo, gave the keynote speech of the event, with a lecture about the history of Quantum Monte Carlo methods, from early days in the 60s up to nowadays.

Figure 19 TREX Symposium 2024 - Dr David Ceperley, University of Illinois Urbana Champaign (US)

The event continued with lectures and presentations from TREX partners and external experts on the latest developments in quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) methods, also in relation to high-performance computing (HPC). Topics included materials simulations with QMC, method developments, HPC implementations, machine learning for QMC, transcorrelated methods, and others. The event also featured some practical demonstrations to showcase the progress of TREX codes and libraries, including QMCKI and TREXIO.

Figure 20 TREX Symposium 2024 - Nicola Marzari, EPFL and Paul Scherrer Institut

WP7 ensured visibility to the event from the very beginning, and Trust-IT Services worked hand in hand with LIST and the University of Twente to have the event page live, keep the agenda updated, manage invitations and monitor registration. During the event, live social media coverage was ensured, together with photo shooting and interviews recorded with speakers and experts while in Luxembourg.

Figure 21 TREX Symposium 2024 - Social media coverage

An animated report has been produced after the event, collecting inputs from the sessions, from the interviews with speakers and experts and insights from the event. At the time of writing this deliverable, the report is undergoing proofreading and cross-checking with partners and organisers of the TREX Symposium before being published on the TREX website. A few snapshot previews are provided below.

The TREX Project Final Event underscored the deep connection between QMC progress and access to powerful computing resources. For researchers like Zoran Sukurma (University of Vienna), the importance of continued support for QMC development is clear. Despite the conclusion of the TREX project, the demand for advancements in this computationally-hungry field will only grow.

The TREX Project Final Event also gave reflections on how QMC is rapidly evolving, with researchers exploring how it can be combined with powerful techniques like machine learning and artificial intelligence. Kosuke Nakano (National Institute for Materials Science) talked about recent algorithmic advancements in QMC, demonstrating that the project isn't just about code development, but also about fundamental scientific progress in tackling long-standing QMC challenges.

Emiel Sloopman (University of Twente) exemplified the real-world benefits of the collaborative spirit embodied by TREX. He highlighted the project's role in creating shared, interoperable tools essential for accelerating research in QMC and the necessity for ongoing efforts in developing these integrative tools to avoid the fragmentation of research into isolated islands.

Giuseppe Carleo (EPFL), while not directly part of TREX, emphasised the value of interactions fostered by such projects. He also underscored the need for future initiatives that support code development, open-source practices, and collaborations between scientists and software engineers to advance computational science and make sophisticated tools widely accessible.

Michele Casula (CNRS Paris), a key contributor to TREX, emphasised the inseparable nature of software advances and scientific discoveries. His breakthrough work on the hydrogen phase diagram and proton transfer mechanisms was directly enabled by code optimization and the efficient GPU porting of the TurboRVB. This is an example of how QMC researchers and HPC experts must work in tandem to unlock the full potential of both hardware and algorithms.

Matthias Rupp (Luxembourg Institute of Science & Technology) delved into the potential of machine learning for accelerating QMC simulations. He discussed how AI techniques can identify correlations and streamline calculations, but also acknowledged the need to understand these complex models to ensure a better understanding of how the models work.

IT'S ABOUT CULTIVATING A COMMUNITY POISED TO TACKLE THE GRAND CHALLENGES OF OUR TIME, WITH QMC INNOVATION AT THE HEART OF THIS QUEST FOR KNOWLEDGE.

A Success Story: Meet Liam Bernheimer, Winner of the TREX School QMC TurboRVB 2023 Poster Competition as a beacon of innovation.

In a notable highlight from the TREX School QMC TurboRVB 2023, Liam Bernheimer, a dedicated PhD student from Tel Aviv University, emerged as the victor of the poster presentation session. His journey into the realm of Quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) technologies is a great example of the innovative spirit driving the next generation of quantum researchers. Bernheimer's work focuses on the development of groundbreaking Monte Carlo algorithms and methods for quantum systems, reflecting a deep engagement with the foundational aspects of QMC methodologies.

Liam Bernheimer's story is a testament to the impact initiatives like the TREX project have on developing emerging talent. The TREX School, with its poster competition, offered both recognition for exceptional early-career researchers and a platform for them to connect with leaders in their field. Programs like this are instrumental in propelling QMC research forward, not just by advancing the tools and methods, but also by training and empowering the next generation of innovators.

"...there are a lot of people who really pioneered the quantum Monte Carlo..."
"...it's interesting to see this point of view that I'm not usually seeing..."

With these words Liam highlighted the opportunity to interact with pioneers in QMC, gaining mentorship and insights that shape his own research. Attending TREX events has also exposed Bernheimer to the real-world uses of QMC tools.

Liam Bernheimer, a PhD student from Tel Aviv University, was the winner of the TREX School QMC TurboRVB 2023 poster competition and was invited as a guest to attend the TREX Symposium and to present as speaker. He gave a presentation on his research about "Path Integral-Enabled Methods within the Stochastic Representation of Wavefunctions". His journey into the realm of Quantum Monte Carlo technologies is a great example of the innovative spirit driving the next generation of quantum researchers, and the true collaborative environment that TREX achieved in creating.

The complete list of participants to the Symposium is provided in Annex III.

Figure 22 Post event report from the TREX Symposium

The promotion of TREX results is at the core of the project dissemination plan and its activities. In this Section, we will detail how the activities listed below have been promoted and disseminated.

TREX implemented its campaigns with a special focus on its organised events (workshops, trainings, and webinars), project outputs, and assets with a SMART approach, ensuring they are specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, and timely. To effectively engage with a target audience, the following activities were implemented as part of the engagement campaign in collaboration with WP6.

- **Agenda:** Collaborated closely with the consortium to define the timing and goals for each webinar, setting audience expectations and categories of discussion.
- **Registration and logistics:** WP7 managed registration on the TREX website, as well as organising the poster procedures on a webpage. For the online event, we conducted rehearsal before the event to ensure smooth slides and address any issues.
- **Engagement campaigns:** Outfocused on technological, topic-oriented, and project-specific themes, reaching communities through channels like and related HPC communities such as psi-K, CECAM, and EuroCC communities.
- **Promotional campaign:** Designed branded event banners, sent personalised email invitations, launched a special edition newsletter, and engaged in social media campaigns. WP7 communicated with registered participants via email and live-tweeted during the event.
- **Post-event activities:** We prepared an official post-event report summarising outputs and recommendations, promoted on platforms like Zenodo. We sent thank-you messages to participants and speakers within 48 hours and shared recorded videos.
- **Video recordings:** Recordings of online events were published on the event page and TREX YouTube channel as soon as the recording was available.

Through these comprehensive engagement strategies, TREX strives to maximise the impact of its campaigns, ensuring valuable insights and knowledge sharing are effectively shared across the community.

TREX also offered attendees the chance to share intriguing research and results through poster sessions at events such as TREX School on QMC with TurboRVB (July 2023), QMC Hands-on Summer Workshop (June 2022), and TREX e-School on Quantum Monte Carlo with TurboRVB (July 2021). Winners received exciting prizes from the TREX team.

3. TREX participation in HPC events

In the reporting period, TREX has been actively participating in several third-party events which served as opportunities to showcase expertise and research, exchange knowledge and establish collaborations with a diverse audience of scientists, researchers, and industry professionals. For each event, WP7 has contributed to amplify engagement and dissemination efforts by managing the following:

- Creation of web pages announcing the TREX participation in these events to inform the community enhancing visibility.
- Social media promotion mainly through Twitter and LinkedIn.
- Newsletter promotion including event details, highlights, and relevant updates for the TREX community.
- Support for the creation of flyers, posters, and other graphical assets needed for the events.
- Publication of presentations and posters from the events on its website.

A selection of key events are reported in the following chapters.

3.1. TREX Tutorials in Theoretical Chemistry at TCCM Winter Schools

TREX has been actively involved in the "TCCM Winter School for Advanced Sciences of Luchon: Tutorials in Theoretical Chemistry" for four consecutive years from 2021 to 2024, playing also the role of official sponsor in 2022 and 2024.

With a focus on computer implementations and numerical methods, the school provided a platform for students and researchers to enhance their understanding of theoretical chemistry. In both editions, TREX contributed with a dedicated session on Quantum Monte Carlo methods, which provided the participants with tutorials to acquire practical skills in implementing QMC algorithms, performing stochastic sampling, and handling parallel workloads, thereby advancing their computational proficiency in theoretical chemistry and related fields. Claudia Filippi, professor from Twente University and TREX Coordinator, along with Anthony Scemama from Laboratoire de Chimie et Physique Quantiques (LCPQ) at Université Paul Sabatier, Toulouse, have been among the organising committee and the teachers in all editions.

Figure 23 TCCM Winter School for advanced sciences of Luchon: Tutorials in Theoretical Chemistry, Social media and newsletter promotion

3.2. CAMD Summer School 2022 on Electronic Structure Theory and Materials Design

The CAMD Summer School 2022 on Electronic Structure Theory and Materials Design, a summer school focused on electronic structure theory for materials design, was held on 14-19 August 2022, in Helsingør, Denmark. Claudia Filippi, Twente University, TREX project coordinator, participated as one of the speakers and provided lectures together with international experts covering topics such as density functional theory (DFT) and its practical implementation.

Figure 24 CAMD Summer School 2022, Social media promotion

3.3. PSI-k Conference 2022

The Psi-k Conference 2022, the 6th general conference for the global Psi-k community, took place from August 22nd to 25th, 2022, in Lausanne, Switzerland. TREX actively participated by delivering four presentations and showcasing posters featuring its flagship codes, with special attention given to TurboRVB and CHAMP³⁰.

TREX presentations at the Psi-k 2022:

- Sandro's legacy: 3 generations of scientists (Download) - Matteo Calandra, Department of Physics, University of Trento, Italy
- Sandro's contribution to ab initio calculations (Download) - Michele Casula, CNRS and Sorbonne University, Paris, France
- Memory of our daily research and the TurboRVB family of codes (Download) - Kosuke Nakano, SISSA, Condensed matter theory group, JSPS overseas fellow JAIST, School of Information Science, Assistant Professor
- Sandro Sorella: Two of his Gems (Download) - Giuseppe Carleo, Computational Quantum Science Lab Institute of Physics, EPFL - Lausanne - Switzerland

TREX posters:

- TurboGenius: A python suite for implementing workflows with ab initio quantum Monte Carlo code "TurboRVB" - Author: Kosuke Nakano, SISSA, JAIST
- Championing stochastic electronic structure methods with CHAMP - Authors: Ravindra Shinde; Edgar Landinez; Stuart Shepard; Alice Cuzzocrea; Anthony Scemama; Claudia Filippi
- Leveraging stochastic electronic structure methods at the exascale - Authors: Edgar Landinez Borda; Gianfranco Abruscio; Ali Alavi; Vijay Gopal Chilkuri; François Coppens; Claudia Filippi; A. Delval; Michal Hapka; M. Hoffer; William Jalby; Pablo Lopez Rios; Kosuke Nakano; Pablo de Oliveira Castro; R. Panades; Kasia Pernal; Evgeny Posenitskiy; Ravindra Shinde; Adam Sokół; Sandro Sorella; Anthony Scemama

Figure 25 PSI-k Conference 2022, publication of presentation and posters

3.4. TERATEC Forum

TREX participated in the TERATEC Forum for two consecutive years:

- June 14–15, 2022, at École Polytechnique, Palaiseau, France
- May 31–June 1, 2023, at Parc Floral in Paris, France

Figure 26 Promotion of TERATEC Forum 2022-2023

During both editions Michele Casula (CNRS) showcased the TREX poster and materials³¹ in a dedicated TREX booth placed in the Europa Village, a specific area of the event dedicated to the European HPC ecosystem.

³⁰ <https://trex-coe.eu/events/psi-k-2022-conference>

³¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/8043226>

3.5. EuroHPC Summit

TREX participated in the EuroHPC Summit 2023 with a dedicated poster titled “Leveraging stochastic electronic structure methods at the exascale” which highlighted the full range of flagship quantum Monte Carlo codes developed by the project as well as its libraries to enhance interoperability.

Figure 27 EuroHPC Summit Week, Social media promotion

3.6. Collaboration with other relevant initiatives

In this reporting period TREX continued to maintain and nurture collaborations with relevant HPC CoEs: MaX CoE, in the context of TREX work with the AiIDA materials informatics platform for workflow management and data storage, and NOMAD for the inclusion of TREXIO library in the NOMAD flagship code. The collaboration continued also with National Competence Centers, such as the Swedish National Competence Center (NCC), the Slovakian, Austrian, and Czech NCCs, as well as European HPC systems (Leonardo, LUMI, and others). Details about the collaborations established and the outcomes achieved are reported in “D8.4 Final Activity Report”, while below we provide details about the events that were co-organised with some of the above mentioned initiatives in the reporting period M19-M42.

Within the framework of such collaborations TREX has actively participated in various events and initiatives aimed at fostering synergies and advancing the field of quantum chemistry and computational materials science.

The TREX CoE and the EuroCC National Competence Center Sweden³² (ENCCS) co-organized an **online workshop** titled “**Targeting Chemical Accuracy with Quantum Monte Carlo on LUMI**” from 26 to 31 January 2023. The event offered Ph.D. students and young researchers practical experience with QMC methods using Quantum Package and CHAMP codes on LUMI, Europe's fastest supercomputer. It featured lectures and hands-on sessions, receiving positive feedback from participants. Gratitude was extended to CSC, LUMI, and ENCCS collaborators. The workshop is expected to foster future collaborative efforts leveraging LUMI and other EuroHPC JU systems.

³² <https://enccs.se/>

TREX collaborated with the **CALMIP** supercomputing centre³³ for a **three-day event in Toulouse from 21 to 23 November 2022** at Espace Clément Ader in Toulouse, France. This event focused on MAQAO for performance analysis, Verificarlo for debugging floating point precision, and StarPU for heterogeneous multicore architectures. Throughout the workshop, instructors introduced the tools, leading to interactive hands-on sessions where participants had the opportunity to potentially apply the tools to their codes.

From **3 to 5 October, 2022 in Lausanne, Switzerland**, the Workshop on HPC Co-design in Computational Materials and Molecular Science, organised by **NOMAD CoE** in partnership with BioExcel, MaX, and TREX, convened top scientists, technologists, and engineers from academia, HPC centres, hardware vendors, and industry. Focused on materials and molecular science, it delved into co-design opportunities between software and hardware developers, aiming to optimise HPC processors and software stacks, including compilers, libraries, schedulers, IO, and containers.

The 10th edition of the **OpenMolcas** developers' workshop, held from **8 to 10 June 2022**, in Uppsala, brought together developers, users, and enthusiasts of the project. Anthony Scemama (CNRS/Toulouse, France) presented the TREXIO file format and library, offering an external perspective and opening doors for new collaborations, particularly in the latest QMC research developments.

³³ <https://www.calmip.univ-toulouse.fr/>

4. Communication activities

TREX communication partner, Trust-IT Services, has strictly cooperated with all partners to maximise the visibility and awareness of the project’s main results and widely disseminate its outcomes.

In particular, to achieve this, TREX's communication and dissemination focused on the following activities:

- Managing the TREX website and generating branded communication materials;
- Producing high-quality content and publications to foster consensus, increase awareness, and cultivate an international TREX community;
- Participating in and organising events
- Ensuring visibility and outreach via social media campaigns across social media platforms and DEM campaigns.

The impact of the communication and dissemination activities was monitored throughout the entire lifespan of the projects with a set of performance metrics whose values are reported in the following sections.

4.1. Website

Throughout the project's duration, the website underwent two major iterations and numerous minor adjustments to enhance the user experience (UX), including streamlined communication and outreach efforts for TREX. Serving as a central hub, the TREX website showcases key assets, results, and analyses, offering a comprehensive repository of valuable information.

Figure 28 TREX Website Information architecture at M42

Dedicated pages for software, training, events and publications have been implemented to further enhance the user experience, ensuring efficient navigation and engagement.

TREX-Codes

In engineering, the ability to optimize materials properties often requires a deep understanding of the relationship between chemical-atomistic structures and the physical properties of the material itself, even both in its solid and fluid phases. Monte Carlo methods allow for a reliable calculation of thermodynamic properties to better predict chemical and physical properties of materials, which is useful not only for engineering but also for science.

TREX developments target eight different codes belonging to the scientific domain of quantum chemistry, not all of them being exclusively QMC codes: **TurboRVB**, **CHAMP**, **QMC=Chem**, **NECI**, **Quantum Package**, **GammCor**, **TREXIO** and **QMckI**.

TREX Open Access codes are available from the TREX CoE Community on Github

<p>TurboRVB TurboRVB is a package for ab initio QMC simulations of both molecular and bulk electronic systems, including electronic structure calculations based on flexible variational wave functions and QMC-driven molecular dynamics simulations for both classical and quantum nuclei.</p> <p>Read More ></p>		
<p>Quantum Package Quantum Package is an electronic structure software focused on wave function methods (configuration interaction) combined with density functional theory.</p> <p>Read More ></p>		

TREX-Libraries

When entering the field of highly specialized scientific disciplines, software development tends to follow rules shared and agreed upon within that specific scientific community, which, however, are often not reusable by others. The goal of TREX is to reimplement the algorithms in a domain-agnostic way such that HPC experts can easily provide the most efficient implementation for exascale hardware.

Within the TREX project, state-of-the-art programs for quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) calculations are analysed to identify key algorithms to be then implemented in human-readable, open-source software QMckI & TREXIO libraries. The libraries are further optimized for future exascale supercomputers by computer scientists of the TREX project. The QMC codes within TREX are at different stages of software development but are all algorithmically extremely advanced and uniquely powerful in the landscape of electronic structure methods.

<p>TREXIO The TREXIO library defines a standard format for storing wave function parameters, together with a C-compatible API such that it can be easily used in any programming language.</p> <p>Read More ></p>	
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Figure 29 Website - Software (TREX Codes and Libraries)

Website Performance. The TREX website has demonstrated satisfactory web traffic, as highlighted by the figures and tables provided below. WP7 monitored the website performance using Google

Analytics³⁴, which tracks user interactions and behaviours, providing essential metrics such as user count, page views, and average engagement rate for insightful analysis.

Direct access serves as the main gateway for users to the website, demonstrating a notable portion of returning visitors who directly input the website URL or search for it on major search engines. Additionally, organic search plays a significant role, reflecting a robust Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) presence for key keywords. Referrals from external websites and social media platforms also contribute to valuable sources of traffic. The majority of website visitors originate from Italy, France, the Netherlands, India, and Germany, in line with the users who actively engaged in TREX events and workshops.

³⁴ TREX's website performance report has been utilising standard Universal Analytics properties since the project's inception on October 1, 2020. Following Google's latest update, we transitioned to Google Analytics 4 starting from July 1, 2023.

Figure 30 Website Performance

The main website's achievements are summarised as follows:

Table 1 TREX Website Performance – Statistics Update

Website Metrics	Performance at M18	Performance at M42
Visitors (Users)	8,916	24,516
Sessions	13,988	38,940
Pageviews	36,101	128,999

The website's performance metrics demonstrate continuous growth in the number of sessions and users both in terms of new and returning users, suggesting an expanding audience base. This is also highlighted by the increase on the pageviews indicating higher levels of user interaction and exploration within the website.

4.2. Social Media

TREX social media platforms X (@trex_eu), LinkedIn (company/trex-eu), and YouTube (@trexproject), played a relevant role in enhancing TREX online presence, facilitating communication and engaging the existing 1.1K online community following TREX on its social media accounts. Through social media, TREX promoted various content, such as QMC flagship codes, libraries, training, videos, webinars, workshops, schools, and participation in third-party events, while also highlighting publications and news relevant to the ecosystem.

Among TREX social media followers on X and LinkedIn, here are some of the relevant communities TREX has liaised with to share content and perform mutual dissemination of relevant posts, news and events

Figure 31 Sample of relevant communities following TREX

X (formerly Twitter) has been mainly used for real-time updates, event promotion, and showcasing project advancements, including scientific perspectives from partners via dedicated cards. It offered comprehensive coverage of live events through "live tweeting" and repurposed project materials for enhanced visibility and accessibility within the community of almost 300 X followers, as demonstrated in the figure below.

Figure 32 Twitter Posts

Table 4 summarises TREX Twitter's main achievements and shows the social media tracker used for regular monitoring.

Table 2 TREX Twitter Performance

Twitter Metrics	Performance at M18	Performance at M42
Followers	209	293
Tweets	165	355

LinkedIn served as a valuable platform for sharing regular updates, promoting activities, engaging with over 800 followers and connections, and expanding the professional community. It is used to generate interest and drive participation in TREX events like workshops and webinars, showcasing the latest developments. Additionally, LinkedIn played a crucial role in onboarding new stakeholders and inviting them to relevant events and webinars. The figures and table below highlight key achievements in LinkedIn outreach activities.

Table 3 TREX LinkedIn Performance

LinkedIn Metrics	Performance at M18	Performance at M42
Followers, Connections	340, 406	419, 411
Posts	80	200

Figure 33 LinkedIn Posts

4.3. TREX Papers and Publications

TREX has made significant effort in disseminating its research findings through various channels. To date, the consortium counts 38 scientific articles published in reputable peer-reviewed journals³⁵, showcasing the depth and breadth of its contributions to the scientific community. Additionally, 6 posters, disseminating key research advancements, were presented at prominent conferences across Europe, serving as visual representations of TREX's cutting-edge work. Furthermore, to facilitate knowledge sharing and broader outreach, 16 sets of presentations and training materials have been compiled and published in the TREX Zenodo community³⁶. The complete list of the TREX publications is also available in ANNEX II.

³⁵ https://trex-coe.eu/publications?field_type_content_target_id=7&page=3

³⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/trex>

Publications

Want to learn more about TREX? On this page, you can find our archive of informative publication materials: reports, deliverables, presentations and articles from experts within the TREX community speaking about various TREX related topics. All the public materials published by TREX partners are available on the [TREX Zenodo Community](#).

- Any - **Articles** Posters Presentations Reports Deliverables

ARTICLES 08 JUL 2022

High-pressure hydrogen by machine learning and quantum Monte Carlo

Andrea Tirelli, Giacomo Tenti, Kousuke Nakano, Sandro Sorella

<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.106.L041105> <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.106.L041105>

ARTICLES 09 JAN 2023

Principal Deuterium Hugoniot via Quantum Monte Carlo and Δ -learning

Giacomo Tenti, Andrea Tirelli, Kousuke Nakano, Michele Casula, Sandro Sorella

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2301.03570> <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2301.03570> ARXIV <https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.03570>

ARTICLES 30 OCT 2023

Thermal dependence of the hydrated proton and optimal proton transfer in the protonated water hexamer

Félix Mouhat, Matteo Peria, Tommaso Morresi, Rodolphe Vuilleumier, Antonino Marco Saitta, Michele Casula

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-42366-4> <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-42366-4> ARXIV <https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.01825>

Figure 34 Publication section on the website

Newsletters proved to be an effective way of engaging with the community as reported in the table below by the statistics that the Mailchimp tool used to create and send the newsletter. In total, TREX distributed 11 newsletters to 356 subscribers as part of its dissemination activities. The TREX newsletter open rate and click-through rate exceed the average benchmarks, indicating that a significant portion of subscribers are actively engaging with the content and effectively are prompt to take actions.

Table 4 TREX newsletters overview

Newsletter	11 newsletter releases
Subscribers	356 subscribers
Open rate	48.6%
Click-through rate	10.9%
Click-to-open rate	22.6%

Note: The average email open rate is between 15-25%. The average click-through rate is about 2.5%. The average click-to-open rate is between 20-30%

4.4. TREX Dissemination Materials

TREX has developed a diverse range of dissemination materials tailored to various stakeholder groups, including scientific communities, industry partners, and policymakers. These materials include informative posters, engaging videos, personalised branded banners, comprehensive presentations, testimonials, gadgets. Each material was designed to effectively communicate TREX's objectives, achievements, and potential impact in advancing quantum Monte Carlo research and high-performance computing. These dissemination materials serve as resources for raising awareness, fostering collaboration, and promoting the uptake of TREX's innovative solutions across diverse sectors, ultimately building a TREX "Quantum Monte Carlo culture".

Figure 35 TREX participants to the TurboRVB School in Trieste, July 2023, wearing the TREX branded t-shirts

4.4.1. Testimonials

TREX training and education activities catered primarily to early careers and HPC developers in materials science simulations. WP7 launched a testimonial series featuring individuals who have directly benefited from the TREX training and educational programs. This material has been published as well on the related event pages and promoted on the social media channels.

TREX Testimonials

TREX training and education is mainly intended for practitioners, as well as HPC developers in materials science simulations, but also has a strong educational component. Its activities consist of several hands-on workshops for code users and developers, hackathons, and a final school.

These events create new opportunities to facilitate the sharing of ideas among communities in different computational disciplines in molecular and materials science. Importantly, TREX events not only focus on the domain-specific software of TREX but also on how it is integrated on (pre) exascale architectures with the most advanced developments, for example, machine learning and data analytics.

Thus, we launched a testimonial series to give voice to the people who concretely benefit from the TREX training/education. And, stay tuned for the upcoming TREX events.

Inspiring Excellence: Celebrating the Achievements of TREX School QMC TurboRVB 2023 Poster Winners

At TREX School QMC TurboRVB 2023, a showcase of innovation, dedication, and expertise unfolded as participants engaged in a dynamic exploration of quantum materials and computation. The event not only served as a platform for learning but also celebrated the talents of those who exhibited their groundbreaking research through the poster competition.

Testimonial: TREX e-School on Quantum Monte Carlo with TurboRVB

The first TREX e-School was held from 12 to 16 July 2021 as a virtual event titled "TREX e-School on Quantum Monte Carlo with TurboRVB".

Quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) methods belong to one of the most accurate families of numerical approaches for materials and electronic structure calculations. Moreover, the steady increase of computer power in the HPC machines is very much suitable for the development and usage of stochastic ab initio methods, which - beside the high precision - are highly scalable and enjoy a favorable scaling with the system size. To build a large user community, it is of paramount importance to disseminate the knowledge, information, and practice of this kind of methods, particularly among students and young researchers.

Testimonial: TREX QMC Workshop

The QMC Hands-on Summer-Workshop took place from 20-23 June 2022 in Majmircove, Slovakia. The workshop was co-organised by the TREX project, Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAS), Institute of Physics SAS (IPAS), and the National Competence Centre for High Performance Computing (NCC for HPC).

The workshop was structured in a mix of lectures and hands-on sessions, which provided a complete theoretical overview and practical experience with the QMC methods and their application to both molecular (Quantum Package and CHAMP codes) and extended systems (TurboRVB). The codes implement the Variational and Diffusion QMC algorithms. The tutorials and training activities were managed by world-leading experts in the respective fields of QMC who all are part of the TREX European Centre of Excellence in Exascale Computing.

Testimonial: Luchon Winter School of the Erasmus Mundus

During the Luchon Winter School of the Erasmus Mundus training event, held from 23rd of January to 8th of February 2021, Claudia Frisch (TREX coordinator) and Anthony Scemama (scientific partner) from TREX participated by teaching to introduce the basic concepts of Quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) methods and explain how to write a simple

Figure 36 TREX Testimonials (samples)

4.4.2. Videos

Videos played a crucial role in engaging with targeted stakeholders and delivering complex information in a digestible format. The TREX project produced 26 videos, which are hosted on the TREX YouTube channel across five playlists (webinars, interviews, hackathons, events and workshops), which achieved a total of 2026 views.

Videos

In this section, you can find the full collection of TREX videos. Get to know more about the project and the people behind this project, fostering and developing high-performance software solutions for quantum mechanical simulations at the exascale.

"At TREX, we aim to develop, promote, and maintain open source high-performance software solutions in quantum chemistry, ready to leverage on the upcoming exascale architectures."

Antony Scemama, research engineer at CNRS

Subscribe to the TREX YouTube channel to keep updated with our community's latest videos and updates.

To receive regular updates from the TREX community.

Subscribe to the TREX Newsletter

Figure 37 TREX Videos

4.4.3. Training materials

A cornerstone of TREX's dissemination and outreach strategy is the commitment to education and empowerment of researchers, developers and users communities with the essential skills needed to proficiently use QMC methods and the TREX flagship codes and libraries.

One of the primary ways TREX achieves this is through the creation and dissemination of training materials. These materials cover a wide range of topics, including theoretical concepts, practical applications, and hands-on tutorials, aimed at equipping participants with the necessary skills to leverage QMC knowledge and TREX's software suite effectively.

These training materials have been produced mainly to be presented during the several events TREX has organised or participated in, from workshops and summer schools to hackathons, co-located events, as well as webinars.

TREX made these training materials publicly available by uploading them to Zenodo³⁷, a widely used repository for research outputs. Furthermore, to streamline access and promote discoverability, these materials are curated and organised within a dedicated section on the TREX website³⁸, serving as a comprehensive repository for researchers seeking to enhance their computational skills in quantum chemistry.

TREX Training and Educational Programme

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TREX offers an outreach programme to foster the use of the developed HPC codes by developers and users communities and to engage and forge a new generation of highly-skilled computational scientists.

TREX structured training and educational activities cover different facets from technical support to the end-users of the TREX software, hands-on training for code users from academia and industry, and hands-on workshops to forge a new generation of code developers.

TREX Training Offer	
Workshops and summer schools	<p>TREX is organising a series of Workshops, Summer Schools and Training Sessions around Europe also leveraging on synergies with relevant HPC initiatives.</p> <p>Luchon Winter School - TREX Tutorials in Quantum Monte Carlo (QMC), 25 January - 8 February 2021</p> <p>CoEs Co-Design Workshop, 12 March 2021</p> <p>TREX-SISSA Summer School, 12-16 July 2021 - presentations and recordings - Presentations (Zenodo)</p> <p>Luchon Winter School - TREX Tutorials in Theoretical Chemistry, 24 January - 4 February 2022</p>
Hackathons	<p>TREX organises different hackathons with clear focus and defined objectives with multiple stakeholders</p> <p>TREX Build-system Hackathon I, 8-12 November 2021 - Presentations and recordings - Presentations (Zenodo)</p> <p>TREX Hackathon II- 28 February - 3 March 2022 - Presentations and recordings - Presentations (Zenodo)</p>
Satellite and co-located events	<p>TREX is leveraging well-exploited events to reach a large number of users inside the relevant communities. The synergies stemming from these events are also highly valuable for TREX future activities</p> <p>Where to meet TREX - Discover the HPC events</p> <p>Tuning Workshop, VI-HPS, 7-11 Dec 2020</p>
Webinars	<p>While engaging people with workshops is temporarily not possible due to COVID-19 restrictions, webinars constitute an exceptional chance to reach out to potential users in Europe and beyond. TREX organises tailored webinar cycles on specific teaching or training topics in HPC and QMC.</p> <p>TREX High Performance Software Solutions for Quantum Mechanical Simulations at the Exascale, 08 February 2023 - Presentations (Zenodo)</p> <p>TREX - CECAM Webinar - Quantum Monte Carlo HPC Applications in Condensed Matter, Quantum Chemistry and Materials Science - Presentations (Zenodo)</p>

Figure 38 TREX Training Page

³⁷ <https://zenodo.org/communities/trex>

³⁸ <https://trex-coe.eu/trex-training-and-educational-programme>

4.4.4. Branded Materials

A detailed overview of the project's communication kit, visual identity elements, and graphics collateral can be found on the TREX website³⁹. The aim of developing a harmonious branding strategy was to create a recognisable graphic pattern that could be consistently used by the entire consortium across multiple channels, effectively connecting back to TREX.

The team also consolidated the informative digital reports created as part of the graphic materials. One notable example is the posters that the team prepared for different events as dissemination materials that showcase the main assets of the projects.

The digitally designed brand was published both in dedicated sections on the TREX Communication Kit and publication page, which are uploaded to the project's Zenodo⁴⁰ account.

Communication Kit

TREX Brand, logo pack, branding materials and brand guidelines

Here you can find the complete and comprehensive collection of all the project logo versions, and some branding materials.

TREX brand guidelines are also offered, defining rules and standards to use when sharing the TREX brand.

- TREX logo - white version
- TREX logo - coloured version
- TREX Brand guidelines

Project flyers, posters and branded materials:

- TREX Flyer - November 2021
- TREX Roll-up banner - December 2021
- TREX Poster for CECAM Flagship Workshop - Roma, October 2021
- TREX Poster for Teratec - Trieste, May 2022
- TREX Presentations and Posters for Psi-k 2022 Conference - Lausanne, 22-25 August 2022
- TREX Poster for the EuroHPC Summit 2023 - Gothenburg, 20-23 March 2023
- TREX Workshop Flier: Electronic structure methods for strong correlation: theory, computational algorithms, and codes - Poland, April 2023
- TREX Flyer - May 2023
- TREX Roll-up banner - May 2023
- TREX Poster for Teratec Forum 2023 - Paris, 31 May and 1 June 2023

TREX official acknowledgement

Please help us get a better understanding of TREX impact by adding the following acknowledgement to your TREX-related papers and publications

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement #952165. This result only reflects the author's view and the EU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains".

You can download the official EU emblem from different formats and sizes from this page

TREX Communication trends

Access this page to find information related to TREX website traffic and analytics and social media engagement.

Press releases and press clippings

Press releases

- 2 June 2021: TREX e-School on Quantum Monte Carlo with TurboRVB - Read online - download
- 21 October 2020: Providing the research community with unique exascale computational power instruments to push quantum chemistry simulations a step further - Read online - download

Press clippings

- 23 Jun 2020: CORDIS
- 22 Oct 2020: CINECA
- 8 Jun 2021: CORDIS
- 24 Jun 2021: HPCWire
- Aug 2021: PSI.k
- 4 Oct 2021: HPCWire
- 1 Jan 2022: Imperial AC UK

TREX Targeting Real Accuracy at exascale

Leveraging stochastic electronic structure methods at the exascale

TREX Publication, Posters (samples)

Figure 39 TREX Publication, Posters (samples)

³⁹ <https://trex-coe.eu/communication-kit>

⁴⁰ <https://zenodo.org/communities/trex>

5. Conclusion

The TREX initiative has demonstrated that the task of adapting computational codes to contemporary HPC systems, particularly those with GPU accelerators, is far more complex than what is often suggested by HPC vendors. By adopting a co-design approach, integrating the needs of end-users and their algorithms into the hardware development process, and by feeding young scientists with a “quantum Monte Carlo culture”, making them aware of the appealing features of a stochastic way of approaching the many-body problem in quantum physics and chemistry, TREX has been a rather multifaceted project whose findings could be highly beneficial for the chemistry research community as well as the HPC industry and commercial providers.

The TREX community is tiny while quite engaged and spread across regions and countries. TREX acknowledged a steady increase in the numbers of QMC practitioners, thanks also to the communication, dissemination, and engagement activities implemented continuously across the 42 months of the project. The collaboration with all TREX partners, and the continuous alignment with WP6 partners in particular, made WP7’s work effective and smooth, ensured variety in the channels and activities implemented and brought very concrete results which we have highlighted in this report.

From a human perspective, it has been extremely rewarding to work with such an excellent, demanding and visionary community, and we hope that the legacy of TREX will set important milestones for the future of Quantum Monte Carlo methods and in general for the panorama of exascale HPC applications.

ANNEX I - List of TREX organised and participated events

TREX Events

Workshop and Schools, and Hackathons: TREX training and education programme thus consists of several training events and actions, and education efforts. Examples include hands-on workshops for code users and developers, schools, satellite events, hackathons, webinars, large final schools and more.

- Total number of organised events: 14 events
- Total number of participants: 550 participants

Event	Date	Location	Audiences Reached
TREX e-School on Quantum Monte Carlo with TurboRVB	12-16 Jul 2021	Online event	Plenary attendees: 89 Hands-on participants: 24 Speakers and technical support: 3 speakers and 5 support from SISSA and CNRS/Paris
TREX session at the virtual PRACE booth at ISC 2021	24 Jun – 2 Jul 2021	Online event	Visibility to over 2000 international attendees and 84 exhibitors; 30 participants to the session
TREX Build-system hackathon	8-12 Nov 2021	Online event	Plenary attendees: 45 Hands-on participants: 22 Speakers and technical support: 9 speakers and 2 support from CNRS/Toulouse and UVSQ
TREX Hackathon II with TREX event at UVSQ	28 Feb – 4 Mar 2022	Versailles, France	TREX consortium
QMC Hands-on Summer Workshop	20-23 Jun 2022	Mojmírovce, Slovakia	Workshop attendees: 47 registered, 21 Phd and Masters Students selected attendees Speakers: 6 HPC experts Technical support: 3 TREX team supports and 2 from NCC for HPC (Slovakia)
TREX High Performance Software Solutions for Quantum Mechanical Simulations at the Exascale	8 Feb 2023	Webinar, Online	Webinar attendees: 68 Speakers: 13 use case leaders and actual users

TREX Hackathon III with CINECA	6-8 March 2023	Bologna, Italy	TREX consortium and 11 TREX code developers
TREX Workshop on Electronic Structure Methods for Strong Correlation	18-20 April 2023	Lodz, Poland	Workshop attendees: 48 registered, 28 onsite Speakers: 3 experts for the following codes: NECI, Quantum Package, GammCor
TREX Workshop: Code Tuning for the Exascale	5-7 June 2023	Bratislava, Slovakia	Workshop attendees: 32 registrants, 25 onsite Speakers: 8 HPC experts
TREX School on QMC with TurboRVB	3-7 July 2023	Trieste, Italy	Workshop attendees: 72 registrants, 25 onsite Speakers and Tutors: 3 experts and 5 hands-on tutors
TREX Hackathon IV	16-20 October 2023	Chemnitz-Röhrsdorf, Germany	TREX consortium
Quantum Monte Carlo HPC Applications in Condensed Matter, Quantum Chemistry and Materials Science	25 January 2024	Webinar, Online	Joint webinar with CECAM TREX: CNRS, Michele Casula UT, Claudia Filippi IPSAS, Ivan Stich Politechnika Łódzka: Kasia Pernal Max Planck Institute for Solid Research, Ali Alavi Attendees: 145 online participants
Bridging Quantum Monte Carlo and High-Performance Simulations	5-9 February 2024	Esch-sur-Alzette, Luxembourg	TREX Symposium attendees: 76 registrants, 70 onsite Speakers: 29 experts
TREX High Performance Software Solutions for Quantum Mechanical Simulations at the Exascale	20 February 2024	Webinar, Online	92 Webinar registrants, 80 live attendees Speakers: 8 experts

Participation to 3rd party events

HPC ecosystem events, including events organised by/with the HPC Center of Excellence Council (HPC3) and FocusCoE, or resulting from collaborations with other HPC CoEs, HPC advancement events, QMC and stochastic training events and domain-specific industry targeting research and academic audience including students, postdocs, researchers, industrial players and stakeholders working in public administrations.

Total number of organised events: 35 events

	Event	Date, Location	TREX Representative
1	The importance of being H.P.C. Earnest (CECAM webinar series)	18 June 2020, Online event	UT, Claudia Filippi CNRS, Anthony Scemama
2	HPC3 Council	June 2020, Online event	UT, Claudia Filippi
3	CECAM2021 Workshop: Recent developments in quantum Monte Carlo	21-22 October 2020, Rome (IT)	CINECA, Fabio Affinito UT, Claudia Filippi CNRS, Michele Casula SISSA, Sandro Sorella
4	Instructor training workshop for HPC CoEs	1 November 2020, Online event	UVSQ partner
5	Tuning Workshop, Vi-HPS	7-11 December 2020, Online event	UVSQ, Cédric Valensi
6	Luchon Winter School - TREX Tutorials in Quantum Monte Carlo (QMC)	25 January - 8 February 2021, Online event	UT, Claudia Filippi CNRS, Anthony Scemama
7	3rd EMMC International Workshop	2-4 March 2021, Online event	CINECA, Fabio Affinito CNRS/Paris, Michele Casula
8	CoEs Co-Design Workshop	12 March 2021, Online event	CNRS, Anthony Scemama CINECA, Fabio Affinito
9	Helmholtz GPU Hackathon 2021 - Digital Event	15-24 March 2021, Online event	CNRS, Anthony Scemama SISSA, Sandro Sorella KTH, Dirk Pleiter
10	“Library development within TREX” at Gruneis’ Group (NOMAD), Vienna University of Technology	22 April 2021, Online event	CNRS, Anthony Scemama
11	CodeRefinery workshop	10-12 May 2021, Online event 18-20 May 2021, Online event	CNRS, Evgeny Posenitskiy TUL, Kasia Pernal KTH, Johan Hellsvik

	Event	Date, Location	TREX Representative
12	10th ABINIT International Developer Workshop	31 May - 4 June 2021, Online event	UT, Claudia Filippi
13	ISC 2021	24 June – 2 July 2021, Online event	CNRS/Toulouse, Anthony Scemama UVSQ, Cédric Valensi, Pablo de Oliveira Castro, William Jalby
14	NCC-CoE meeting on First-Principle Simulations in Chemistry and Materials Science	1 July 2021, Online event	UT, Claudia Filippi CNRS/Toulouse, Anthony Scemama
15	Workshop on Ontologies for Materials-Databases Interoperability (OMDI2021)	5-7 October 2021, Online event	CNRS/Toulouse partner
16	NCC-CoE meeting on Code Optimization	1 November 2021, Online event	UVSQ, William Jalby
17	FocusCoE Centres of Excellence Webinar Webinar on the interaction with industries and SMEs	1 December 2021, Online event	Megware and CNRS/Paris partners
18	Stochastic Methods in Electronic Structure Theory	6-9 December 2021, Online event	UT, Claudia Filippi, Stuart Shepard, and Ramon Panades CNRS, Michele Casula SISSA, Sandro Sorella & Saverio Moroni
19	Luchon Winter School - TREX Tutorials in Quantum Monte Carlo (QMC)	24 January - 4 February 2022, Online event	UT, Claudia Filippi CNRS, Anthony Scemama
20	EuroHPC Summit Week 2022	22-24 March 2022; Paris, France	CNRS, Anthony Scemama, Vikay Gopal Chilkuri, and Michele Casula UVSQ, Pablo De Oliveira, Cédric Valensi and William Jalby
21	Girls Day University Twente	7 April 2022, Enschede, The Netherlands	3rd-party event (co-sponsored by TREX)
22	The 10th edition OpenMolcas developers' workshop	8-10 June 2022; Uppsala, Sweden	CNRS, Anthony Scemama
23	TERATEC 2022 Forum	14-15 June 2022; Paris, France	CNRS, Michele Casula and Anthony Scemama

	Event	Date, Location	TREX Representative
24	WATOC 2020	3-8 July 2022; Vancouver, Canada	UT, Claudia Filippi, Vijay Gopal Chilkuri IPSAS: Ivan Stich Politechnika Łódzka: Kasia Pernal CNRS: Anthony Scemama
25	CAMD Summer School 2022 on Electronic Structure Theory and Materials Design	14-19 August 2022; Helsingør, Denmark	UT, Claudia Filippi
26	Psi-k 2022 Conference	22-25 August 2022; Lausanne, Switzerland	SISSA: Kosuke Nakano, Giuseppe Carleo CNRS: Michele Casula, UT, Claudia Filippi, Ravindra Shinde; Edgar Landinez; Stuart Shepard; Alice Cuzzocrea, Vijay Gopal Chilkuri, CINECA, Gianfranco Abrusci
27	Co-Design for HPC in Computational Materials and Molecular Science	3-5 October 2022; Lausanne, Switzerland	Joint effort with CECAM and other CoEs: NOMAD, BioExcel and MAX UT, Claudia Filippi CNRS, Anthony Scemama
28	TREX/CALMIP Training	21-23 November 2022; Toulouse, France	Joint training with CALMIP (Espace Clement Ader) Supercomputing Centre CNRS, Anthony Scemama UVSQ, Cédric Valensi
29	Quantum2 on Machine Learning Enhanced Sampling	29 November - 1 December 2023, Lausanne, Switzerland	CNRS, Michele Casula
30	TCCM Winter School for advanced sciences of Luchon - TREX Tutorials in Theoretical Chemistry	23 January - 3 February 2023; Aspet, France	UT, Claudia Filippi CNRS, Anthony Scemama
31	Targeting chemical accuracy with quantum Monte Carlo on LUMI	26-31 January 2023, Online	Joint workshop with ENCCS (EuroCC National Competence Center Sweden) and LUMI

	Event	Date, Location	TREX Representative
32	The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU)	20-23 March 2023; Gothenburg, Sweden	CNRS, Anthony Scemama UVSQ, William Jalby
33	Teratec Forum 2023	31 May - 1 June 2023; Paris, France	CNRS, Michele Casula and Anthony Scemama UVSQ, William Jalby Megware, Axel Auweter
34	TCCM Winter School Lessons & Tutorials in Theoretical Chemistry - TREX tutorials in QMC methods	15-26 January 2024; Aspet, France	UT, Claudia Filippi CNRS, Anthony Scemama
35	DPG Spring Meeting 2024	17-22 March 2024, Berlin, Germany	CNRS, Michele Casula, Marco Cherubini, Abhishek Raghav

ANNEX II - List of publications by TREX participants (M1-M42)

Authors (komma separated)	Title	Title of Journal/Proceedings/Books series	DOI	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
Dominik Lemm, Guido Falk von Rudorff, O. Anatole von Lilienfeld	Machine learning based energy-free structure predictions of molecules (closed and open-shell), transition states, and solids	Nature Communications	10.1038/s41467-021-24525-7	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2102.02806	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-021-24525-7
Jan Weinreich, Nicholas J. Browning, O. Anatole von Lilienfeld	Machine Learning of Free Energies in Chemical Compound Space Using Ensemble Representations: Reaching Experimental Uncertainty for Solvation	The Journal of Chemical Physics	10.1063/5.0041548	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.09722	https://aip.scitation.org/doi/10.1063/5.0041548
Tommaso Morresi, Lorenzo Paulatto, Rodolphe Vuilleumier, Michele Casula	Probing anharmonic phonons by quantum correlators: A path integral approach	The Journal of Chemical Physics	10.1063/5.0050450	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.04094	https://aip.scitation.org/doi/10.1063/5.0050450
Bing Huang, O. Anatole von Lilienfeld	Ab initio machine learning in chemical compound space	Chemical Reviews	10.1021/acs.chemrev.0c01303	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.07502	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.chemrev.0c01303

Authors (komma separated)	Title	Title of Journal/DOI Proceedings/ Books series	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
Monika Dash, Saverio Moroni, Claudia Filippi, Anthony Scemama	Tailoring CIPSI expansions for QMC calculations of electronic excitations: the case study of thiophene	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.01158	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.jctc.1c00212
Vijay Gopal Chilkuri, Thomas Applencourt, Kevin Gasperich, Pierre-François Loos, Anthony Scemama	Spin adaptation with determinant-based selected configuration interaction	Advances in Quantum Chemistry	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2021.04.01812.06902	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0065327621000022
Enrico Tapavicza, Guido Falk von Rudorff, David O. De Haan, Mario Contin, Christian George, Matthieu Riva, O. Anatole von Lilienfeld	Elucidating an Atmospheric Brown Carbon Species—Toward Supplanting Chemical Intuition with Exhaustive Enumeration and Machine Learning	Environmental Science & Technology	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2101.07301	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.est.1c00885
Katarzyna Pernal, Michał Hapka	Range-separated multiconfigurational density functional theory methods	WIREs Computational Molecular Science	Article in Journal	https://wires.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1002/wcms.1566	https://wires.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1002/wcms.1566
Saverio Moroni, Francesco Ancilotto, Pier Luigi	Localization versus inhomogeneous superfluidity:	Physical Review B	Article in Journal	https://journals.aps.org/prb/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevB.103.174514	https://journals.aps.org/prb/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevB.103.174514

Authors (komma separated)	Title	Title of Journal/DOI Proceedings/ Books series	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
Silvestrelli, and Luciano Reatto	Submonolayer 4He on fluorographene, hexagonal boron nitride, and graphene			/10.1103/PhysRevB.103.174514	
W Dobrutz, O Weser, NABogdanov, A. Alavi, G LiManni	Spin-Pure Stochastic-CASSCF via GUGA-FCIQMC Applied to Iron-Sulfur Clusters	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.07775	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jctc.1c00589
Raghavendra Meena, Guanna Li, Michele Casula	Ground-state properties of the narrowest zigzag graphene nanoribbon from quantum Monte Carlo and comparison with density functional theory	The Journal of Chemical Physics	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.06300	https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0078234
Claudia Filippi, Jesse van Rhijn, Stefania De Palo, Saverio Moroni	Energy Derivatives in Real-Space Diffusion Monte Carlo	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.06300	https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0078234
Miha Srdinšek, Michele Casula, Rodolphe Vuilleumier	Quantum Rényi entropy by optimal thermodynamic integration paths	Physical Review Research	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2112.14199	https://journals.aps.org/prresearch/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevResearch.4.L032002

Authors (komma separated)	Title	Title of Journal/DOI Proceedings/ Books series	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
Piotr H. Kowalski, Agnieszka Krzemińska, Katarzyna Pernal, and Ewa Pastorczyk	Dispersion Interactions between Molecules in and out of Equilibrium Geometry: Visualization and Analysis	The Journal of Physical Chemistry	Article in Journal	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpca.2c00004	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpca.2c00004?ref=PDF
Tommaso Morresi, Rodolphe Vuilleumier, Michele Casula	Hydrogen phase-IV characterization by full account of quantum anharmonicity	Physical Review B	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2203.06399	https://journals.aps.org/prb/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevB.106.054109
Dirk Bakowies, O. Anatole von Lilienfeld	Density Functional Geometries and Zero-Point Energies in Ab Initio Thermochemical Treatments of Compounds with First-Row Atoms (H, C, N, O, F)	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	Article in Journal	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.jctc.1c00474	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.jctc.1c00474
Abdallah Ammar, Emmanuel Giner, Anthony Scemama	Optimization of large determinant expansions in quantum Monte Carlo	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.12851	https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.2c00556
Alice Cuzzocrea, Saverio Moroni, Anthony Scemama, Claudia Filippi	Reference Excitation Energies of Increasingly Large Molecules: A QMC Study of Cyanine Dyes	Journal of chemical theory and computation	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.09640	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jctc.1c01162

Authors (komma separeted)	Title	Title of Journal/DOI Proceedings/ Books series	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
Abdallah Ammar, Anthony Scemama, Emmanuel Giner	Extension of selected configuration interaction for transcorrelated methods	Journal of Chemical Physics	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.08399	https://aip.scitation.org/doi/pdf/10.1063/5.0115524
Stuart Shepard, Ramón L. Panadés-Barrueta, Saverio Moroni, Anthony Scemama, Claudia Filippi	Double Excitation Energies from Quantum Monte Carlo Using State-Specific Energy Optimization	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.12160	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acs.jctc.2c00769
Ke Liao, Huanchen Zhai, Evelin Martine Christlmaier, Pablo López Ríos, Daniel Kats, Thomas Schraivogel, and Ali Alavi	Density Matrix Renormalization Group for Transcorrelated Hamiltonians: Ground and Excited States in ab initio Systems	Journal of Chemical Physics	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.00173	https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.00173
J Philip Haupt, Pablo Lopez Rios, Werner Dobrautz, Aron Cohen, and Ali Alavi	Optimizing Jastrow factors for the transcorrelated method	Journal of Chemical Physics	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.13683	https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.13683
Evgeny Posenitskiy, Vijay Gopal Chilkuri, Abdallah Ammar, Michał Hapka, Katarzyna Pernal, Ravindra Shinde, Edgar Josué	TREXIO: A file format and library for quantum chemistry	Journal of Chemical Physics	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.14793	https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0148161

Authors (komma separeted)	Title	Title of Journal/DOI Proceedings/ Books series	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
Landinez Borda, Claudia Filippi, Kosuke Nakano, Otto Kohulák, Sandro Sorella, Pablo de Oliveira Castro, William Jalby, Pablo López Ríos, Ali Alavi, Anthony Scemama					
Thomas Schraivogel, Evelin Martine Christlmaier, Pablo López Ríos, Ali Alavi, Daniel Kats	Transcorrelated coupled cluster methods. II. Molecular systems	Journal of Chemical Physics	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.12903	https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0151412
Ke Liao, Huanchen Zhai, Evelin Martine Christlmaier, Thomas Schraivogel, Pablo López Ríos, Daniel Kats, Ali Alavi	Density Matrix Renormalization Group for Transcorrelated Hamiltonians: Ground and Excited States in Molecules	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.00173	https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.2c01207
J. Philip Haupt, Seyed Mohammadreza Hosseini, Pablo Lopez Rios, Werner Dobrautz, Aron Cohen, Ali Alavi	Optimizing Jastrow factors for the transcorrelated method	Journal of Chemical Physics	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.13683	https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0147877

Authors (komma separated)	Title	Title of Journal/Proceedings/Books series	DOI	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
Evelin Martine Christlmaier, Thomas Schraivogel, Pablo López Ríos, Ali Alavi, Daniel Kats	xTC: An efficient treatment of three-body interactions in transcorrelated methods	Journal of Chemical Physics	10.1063/5.0154445	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.07006	https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0154445
Giovanni Li Manni, Ignacio Fernández Galván, Ali Alavi, Flavia Aleotti, Francesco Aquilante, Jochen Autschbach, Davide Avagliano, Alberto Baiardi, Jie J. Bao, Stefano Battaglia, Letitia Birnoschi, Alejandro Blanco-González, Sergey I. Bokarev, Ria Broer, Roberto Cacciari, Paul B. Calio, Rebecca K. Carlson, Rafael Carvalho Couto, Luis Cerdán, Liviu F. Chibotaru, Nicolas F. Chilton, Jonathan Richard Church, Irene Conti, Sonia Coriani, Juliana Cuéllar-Zuquin, Razan E. Daoud, Nike Dattani, Piero Decleva, Coen de Graaf,	The OpenMolcas Web: A Community-Driven Approach to Advancing Computational Chemistry	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	10.1021/acs.jctc.3c00182	Article in Journal	https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2023-b7f0j-v2	https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.3c00182

Authors (komma separeted)	Title	Title of Journal/DOI Proceedings/ Books series	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
Mickaël G. Delcey, Luca De Vico, Werner Dobrautz, Sijia S. Dong, Rulin Feng, Nicolas Ferré, Michael Filatov (Gulak), Laura Gagliardi, Marco Garavelli, Leticia González, Yafu Guan, Meiyuan Guo, Matthew R. Hennefarth, Matthew R. Hermes, Chad E. Hoyer, Miquel Huix-Rotllant, Vishal Kumar Jaiswal, Andy Kaiser, Danil S. Kaliakin, Marjan Khamesian, Daniel S. King, Vladislav Kochetov, Marek Krośnicki, Arpit Arun Kumaar, Ernst D. Larsson, Susi Lehtola, Marie-Bernadette Lepetit, Hans Lischka, Pablo López Ríos, Marcus Lundberg, Dongxia Ma, Sebastian Mai, Philipp Marquetand, Isabella C. D. Merritt, Francesco Montorsi, Maximilian					

Authors (komma separeted)	Title	Title of Journal/DOI Proceedings/ Books series	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
Mörchen, Artur Nenov, Vu Ha Anh Nguyen, Yoshio Nishimoto, Meagan S. Oakley, Massimo Olivucci, Markus Oppel, Daniele Padula, Riddhish Pandharkar, Quan Manh Phung, Felix Plasser, Gerardo Raggi, Elisa Rebolini, Markus Reiher, Ivan Rivalta, Daniel Roca-Sanjuán, Thies Romig, Arta Anushirwan Safari, Aitor Sánchez-Mansilla, Andrew M. Sand, Igor Schapiro, Thais R. Scott, Javier Segarra-Martí, Francesco Segatta, Dumitru-Claudiu Sergentu, Prachi Sharma, Ron Shepard, Yinan Shu, Jakob K. Staab, Tjerk P. Straatsma, Lasse Kragh Sørensen, Bruno Nunes Cabral Tenorio, Donald G. Truhlar, Liviu Ungur,					

Authors (komma separeted)	Title	Title of Journal/DOI Proceedings/ Books series	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
Morgane Vacher, Valera Veryazov, Torben Arne Voß, Oskar Weser, Dihua Wu, Xuchun Yang, David Yarkony, Chen Zhou, J. Patrick Zobel, Roland Lindh					
Lorenzo Monacelli, Michele Casula, Kousuke Nakano, Sandro Sorella, Francesco Mauri	Quantum phase diagram of high-pressure hydrogen	Nature Physics	10.1038/s41567-023-01960-5	Article in Journal https://arxiv.org/abs/2202.05740	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41567-023-01960-5
Giacomo Tenti, Andrea Tirelli, Kousuke Nakano, Michele Casula, Sandro Sorella	Principal Deuterium Hugoniot via Quantum Monte Carlo and Δ -learning	arXiv preprint	10.48550/arXiv.2301.01825	Other https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.03570	https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.03570
Marcel F. Langer, Florian Knoop, Christian Carbogno, Matthias Scheffler, Matthias Rupp	Heat Flux for Semilocal Machine-Learning Potentials	Physical Review B	10.1103/physrevb.108.1100302	Article in Journal https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.14434	https://doi.org/10.1103/physrevb.108.1100302
Félix Mouhat, Matteo Peria, Tommaso Morresi, Rodolphe Vuilleumier, Antonino Marco Saitta, Michele Casula	Thermal Dependence of the Hydrated Proton and Optimal Proton Transfer in the Protonated Water Hexamer	Nature Communications	10.1038/s41467-023-42366-4	Article in Journal https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.01825	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-023-42366-4

Authors (komma separated)	Title	Title of Journal/DOI Proceedings/ Books series	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
Stephen R. Xie, Matthias Rupp, Richard G. Hennig	Ultra-Fast Interpretable Machine-Learning Potentials	npj Computational Materials	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2110.00624	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41524-023-01092-7
Andrea Tirelli, Giacomo Tenti, Kousuke Nakano, and Sandro Sorella	High-pressure hydrogen by machine learning and quantum Monte Carlo	Phys. Rev. B	Article in Journal	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2112.11099	https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.106.L041105
Michał Hapka, Agnieszka Krzeminska, Marcin Modrzejewski, Michał Przybytek, Katarzyna Pernal	Efficient Calculation of the Dispersion Energy for Multireference Systems with Cholesky Decomposition: Application to Excited-State Interactions	The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.01547	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.3c01568?ref=pdf
Mohammad Reza Jangrouei, Agnieszka Krzeminska, Michał Hapka, Ewa Pastorczak, Katarzyna Pernal	Dispersion Interactions in Exciton-Localized States. Theory and Applications to π - π^* and n - π^* Excited States	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	Article in Journal	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jctc.2c00221	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jctc.2c00221
Miha Srdinšek, Michele Casula, Rodolphe Vuilleumier	Rényi entropy of a quantum anharmonic	Physical Review B	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/html/2303.04768v2	https://journals.aps.org/prb/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevB.108.245121

Authors (komma separated)	Title	Title of Journal/DOI Proceedings/ Books series	Type	Repository Link	Link to the publication
	chain at nonzero temperature				
Romain Taureau, Marco Cherubini, Tommaso Morresi, Michele Casula	Quantum symmetrization transition in superconducting sulfur hydride from quantum Monte Carlo and path integral molecular dynamics	npj Computational Materials	Article in Journal	https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.15684	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41524-024-01239-0

ANNEX III - List of participants to the TREX Symposium 2024

#	First Name	Last Name	Country/ Region	Organization
1	Ali	Alavi	Germany	Max Planck Society
2	Abdallah	Ammar	France	LCPO, CNRS
3	Axel	Auweter	Germany	MEGWARE
4	Sepideh	Bagheri	Iran	Iran University of Science and Technology
5	Matteo	Barborini	Luxembourg	University of Luxembourg
6	Jamel	Bawre	Ghana	Underground Mining Alliance
7	Jan	Beerens	Netherlands	University of Twente
8	Anouar	Benali	United States	Argonne National Laboratory
9	Liam	Bernheimer	Israel	Tel Aviv University
10	Daniel	Bibik	Germany	Heidelberg University
11	Jan	Brndiar	Slovakia	Institute of Informatics Slovak Academy of Sciences (IISAS)
12	Giuseppe	Carleo	Switzerland	EPFL
13	Michele	Casula	France	CNRS and Sorbonne Université
14	David	Ceperley	United States	University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
15	Jorge	Charry	Luxembourg	University of Luxembourg
16	Marco	Cherubini	Italy	Institut de Mineralogie, de Physique de Matériaux et de Cosmochimie, CNRS, Sorbonne University
17	Matej	Ditte	Luxembourg	University of Luxembourg
18	Robert	Doe	Ghana	Bob Doe Ventures
19	rim	doukha	Luxembourg	ANEC
20	Jean Baptiste	Fankam Fankam	South Africa	University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa
21	Claudia	Filippi	Netherlands	University of Twente
22	VIDIT	GANGWAR	India	Dr B R Ambedkar National Institute of Technology Jalandhar Punjab, India
23	Peter	Gill	Australia	University of Sydney
24	Emmanue l	Giner	France	CNRS

#	First Name	Last Name	Country/ Region	Organization
25	Vitaly	Gorelov	France	CNRS, Ecole Polytechnique (LSI)
26	Michal	Hapka	Poland	University of Warsaw
27	Yongda	Huang	China	Slovak academy of sciences
28	Moritz	Humer	Austria	University of Vienna
29	Shoaib	Hyder	India	Computacenter India Pvt Ltd
30	Tom	Ichibha	Japan	Japan Advanced Institute of Science and Technology
31	Asif	Iqbal	Belgium	Ghent university
32	El Mostafa	Jalal	Morocco	Sultan Moulay Slimane University
33	Paul	Kent	United States	Oak Ridge National Laboratory
34	Oto	Kohulak	Slovakia	CNRS
35	Edgar Josue	Landinez Borda	Netherlands	University of Twente
36	Luca	Leoni	Italy	University of Bologna
37	Pablo	Lopez Rios	Germany	Max-Planck institute for Solid State Research
38	Dixisset	Loremipsum	Luxembourg	Oratione
39	Ryo	Maezono	Japan	JAIST
40	Ilja	Makkonen	Finland	University of Helsinki
41	Nicola	Marzari	Switzerland	EPEL
42	Michel	Masella	France	CEA
43	Bijal	Mehta	India	Sardar Vallabhbhai National Institute of Technology
44	Lubos	Mitas	United States	North Carolina State University
45	Felix	Moncada	Colombia	Stockholm University
46	Miguel	Morales Silva	United States	Flatiron Institute
47	Saverio	Moroni	Italy	CNR-IOM, Trieste, Italy
48	Kosuke	Nakano	Japan	National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS)
49	Matteo	Peria	France	IMPPMC - CNRS/Sorbonne Université

#	First Name	Last Name	Country/ Region	Organization
50	Kasia	PErnal	Poland	Lodz University of Technology
51	Carlo	Pierleoni	Italy	University of L'Aquila
52	Sara	Pittonet Gaiarin	Italy	Trust-IT Services
53	Peshal	Pokharel	Nepal	Central Department of Physics Tribhuvan University
54	Evgeny	Posenitskiy	France	Qubit Pharmaceuticals
55	Abhishek	Raghav	France	IMPMC, Sorbonne University
56	Brenda	Rubenstein	United States	Brown University
57	Matthias	Rupp	Luxembourg	Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST)
58	Anthony	Scemama	France	CNRS
59	Martin	Schlipf	Austria	VASP Software GmbH
60	Mladen	Skelin	Luxembourg	EuroHPC JU
61	Emiel	Slootman	Netherlands	University of Twente
62	PRADHI	SRIVASTAVA	India	Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Bhopal India
63	Ivan	STICH	Slovakia	Inst. of Informatics, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava, Slovakia
64	Zoran	Sukurma	Austria	university of Vienna
65	Aleksandra	Tucholska	Poland	Lodz University of Technology
66	Cyrus	Umrigar	United States	Cornell University
67	Valerio	Vitale	Italy	University of Trieste
68	Lucas	Wagner	United States	University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
69	Andrea	Zen	Italy	Università di Napoli Federico II
70	Shiwei	Zhang	United States	Flatiron Institute